

1 **Exploring climate-induced sex-based differences in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems to**
2 **mitigate biodiversity loss**

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18 **SUMMARY:** Aquatic and terrestrial organisms respond to climate change differently by biological
19 sex. A key challenge is to unravel the relative contribution of sex and climate change in the response
20 mechanisms of individuals and the related cascading effects to populations and communities. This
21 new understanding is essential to improve climate adaptation and mitigation strategies.

22

23 Challenges posed by climate change threaten ecosystems, the crucial benefits they provide to people,
24 and, ultimately, human livelihoods and lives. Global warming impacts ecological systems and
25 processes across continents and oceans, resulting in changes to the phenology, distribution and
26 behaviour of organisms, persistence and dynamics of populations, and structure and function of
27 species assemblages and ecosystems. In the Anthropocene, a deeper understanding of the biological
28 impacts of climate change, as well as innovative solutions are needed to reverse climate-induced
29 biodiversity loss.

30 One largely ignored dimension in research and conservation is how organisms respond to climate
31 change differently by biological sex^{1,2}. Sex is frequently not reported or tested likely because
32 researchers are not aware of sex-based differences, assume that including sex-specific information
33 would not influence experimental results³, or are unable to obtain sex-specific data. Here, we focus
34 on sex-based differences across terrestrial and aquatic domains. We argue that studying sex-based
35 differences from organisms to populations and communities may generate new insights in resilience
36 and vulnerability to climate stressors not otherwise recognized.

37

38 ***Sex influences responses of organisms, populations, and communities to climate change***

39 *Organisms.* Sex-specific responses to climate change have been documented across a broad range of
40 ecosystems and taxa, from plants to invertebrates, fish, mammals and birds⁴. The broad range of sex-
41 specific responses to different climate stressors is illustrated through selected examples in Fig. 1 and
42 described in more detail below.

43 At the organismal level, individuals can display sex-specific responses to climate stressors that affect
44 traits such as body size, growth rates, survival, age, or size at first reproduction, and other life history
45 traits that influence reproductive output and population persistence and dynamics. For instance, the
46 1988/9 climate regime shift – involving changes in the Pacific Decadal Oscillation Index, the Aleutian
47 Low Pressure Index, sea surface temperature, and zooplankton biomass – triggered sex-specific

48 changes in life-history traits of Korean chum salmon (*Oncorhynchus keta*) populations⁵ (Fig. 1a).
49 Males and females displayed different maturation schedule and growth in response to the climate
50 shift, with a decrease in body size and an increase in age at spawning in females. By contrast, females
51 of Arctic wolf spiders (*Pardosa glacialis*) were found to increase in adult body size due to earlier
52 snowmelt more than males⁶ (Fig. 1b). These changes likely decrease reproductive success in Korean
53 chum salmon⁵ and increase reproductive success of Arctic wolf spiders⁶.

54 *Populations.* Monitoring pre-existing sex ratios and exploring factors governing sex ratio
55 mechanisms in natural populations (e.g., mating behaviour, predation, food availability) in
56 combination with climate-induced sex-specific effects is essential to understand the downstream
57 effects of sex and climate stressors on population growth compared to what is expected if the effect
58 was averaged across the two sexes. In species with temperature-dependent sex determination, an
59 increase in temperature experienced during embryonic development leads, for instance, to more
60 females than males in hatchling sex ratios in green sea turtles (*Chelonia mydas*)⁷ and more males than
61 females in tuatara (*Sphenodon guntheri*)⁸ (Fig. 1h). When exposed to increasing temperatures, two
62 populations of Atlantic marine copepod (*Acartia tonsa*) males showed significantly lower survival
63 than females in response to warming⁹ (Fig. 1c). Reduced reproductive success resulting from greater
64 male mortality and therefore sperm limitation may lead to population decline⁹. Since copulation is
65 necessary for the production of viable eggs¹⁰, any factor that skews sex ratios toward females
66 and away from males might adversely affect population growth rates through mating
67 limitation^{10,11}. In natural copepod populations, female-skewed ratios are often observed¹⁰. In a
68 scenario of increasing temperature, climate-induced male mortality in pre-existing female-skewed
69 copepod populations can affect male-female encounter rates and mating success over time more
70 severely than if thermal performance was similar across sexes. In the case of Australian flying foxes,
71 females showed significantly lower survival than males in response to thermal extremes¹² (Fig. 1d).
72 Uneven thermal tolerance by males and females causing severe sex ratio distortion in natural

73 populations can affect reproductive success and population viability. Skewed sex ratios can increase
74 mating competition and decrease mating success, limit fertilization rates and breeding opportunities,
75 and decrease genetic diversity--all of which impacts population dynamics and growth^{13,14}. In addition,
76 changes in fertility of males and females induced by climate change – such as the decrease of
77 production and viability of eggs and sperm until sterility¹⁵ – reduce reproductive performance¹⁶
78 worsening the effects on populations in combination with the other sex-specific effects mentioned
79 before.

80 Females and males tend to respond differently to climate-induced environmental changes in species
81 where females and males have different energetic requirements, foraging behaviours or habitat
82 preferences (Fig. 1e-g). For instance, male and female Pacific walrus (*Odobenus rosmarus*
83 *divergens*) segregate spatially in the Arctic, with females depending on sea-ice cover for breeding
84 and nursery more than males¹⁷. A climate-induced reduction in sea ice in the Chukchi Sea forced
85 females to use terrestrial haul-outs instead of sea-ice sites to rest and nurse while foraging in offshore
86 grounds. (Fig. 1e). This has increased the time in the water required to reach foraging grounds, which
87 may deplete energy and substantially decrease lactation and limit offspring nutrition, potentially
88 reducing juvenile survival¹⁸. These climate-induced changes can negatively impact reproductive
89 capacity, population persistence and growth¹⁹, and increased mortality has already been observed as
90 a consequence of juveniles being trampled in terrestrial haul-outs²⁰. Similarly, male and female
91 Caribou (*Rangifer tarandus*) segregate spatially following different strategies to maximize
92 reproductive success: males to maximize pre-rut energy reserves and promote successful competition
93 with other males for mates, and females to promote offspring growth and survival²¹. A reduction in
94 high quality (i.e., nitrogen-rich) forage means female caribou are likely to move northwards to support
95 breeding and lactation which exposes them to more predators during migration²² (Fig. 1f). In the case
96 of sexually size-dimorphic seabird populations of Southern Atlantic giant petrels (*Macronectes halli*
97 and *M. giganteus*), sex-specific ecological differences can lead to divergent responses to climate-

98 induced changes combined with other environmental drivers (Fig. 1g). Females – smaller than males
99 – for example, rely on pelagic resources for foraging more than males and are more sensitive to
100 increases in variation in oceanographic conditions, sea ice concentration, and fishing effort through
101 entanglements. Females also benefit from stronger meridional winds likely because increased flight
102 speed improves foraging performance. Males, by contrast, rely on terrestrial foraging more than
103 females and are more sensitive to changes in the availability of land-based carrion. Males are also
104 affected by stronger meridional winds likely because of indirect effects from wind-driven changes in
105 oceanographic conditions²³.

106 Ignoring sex-based differences leads to underestimates of the relative influence of a changing
107 environment on terrestrial and aquatic populations. More critically, pooling sex-specific data may
108 result in not detecting any effect of environmental drivers or in overestimating effects at population
109 level. In the case of North giant petrels, survival effects were unapparent when females and males
110 were considered together²³. In a case of snowy plovers (*Charadrius nivosus*), population viability
111 was significantly overestimated when sex ratio and mating system were ignored²⁴. Similarly, in a
112 theoretical model of a two-sex spreading population, population invasion was overestimated when
113 sex differences in demographic and dispersal parameters, and the sex-specific mechanics of locating
114 mates were overlooked²⁵.

115 *Communities*. Sex-specific responses at the species and population levels may impact community
116 dynamics and energy transfer throughout food webs, with consequences for the benefits that humans
117 derive from ecosystems, as we see in the example of Arctic Northern shrimp and related Greenland
118 shrimp fishery production (Fig. 1j). Northern shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*) are protandric
119 hermaphrodites functioning first as males, then undergoing a transitional phase and becoming
120 females, and the Greenland shrimp fishery production relies on Arctic Northern shrimp stock
121 availability²⁶. Ocean acidification and warmer temperatures slow Northern shrimp development such
122 that their transition from male to female no longer coincides with the spring phytoplankton bloom,

123 the major food source for larvae. This prolongs the larval vulnerability to predation, with negative
124 impacts on recruitment rates. These climate-induced changes might underlie the decreased shrimp
125 catch rates in this region and the subsequent effects on local employment and economies where
126 fishery processing facilities have already been closing due to a decrease in catch rates since 2012 and
127 whose causes until now remain unclear²⁶. To fully understand biological responses to climate change,
128 community-level consequences of sex-specific differences at individual and population levels need
129 to be investigated for the higher-order patterns they reveal²⁷ (examples in Table 1). Climate change
130 predictions that assume that all individuals of a species are phenotypically identical²⁸ may miss
131 critical sex-based intraspecific variability²⁹.

132

133 ***Taking action to reverse biodiversity loss***

134 Sex influences the response of living organisms to climate change in many different ways. Decision
135 makers, researchers, and funding agencies can act to use this knowledge and produce new insights to
136 advance the fields of climate change biology with the goal of reversing biodiversity loss (Text box
137 1).

138 Decision makers can improve adaptation and mitigation policies by leveraging knowledge about sex-
139 specific differences in response to climate change. For example, to counter the impacts of increasing
140 sand temperatures negatively impacting hatchling sex ratio and hatching success of eggs in six species
141 of marine turtles, the Queensland Government in Australia³⁰ has established a conservation strategy
142 to implement practical nest cooling techniques, such as nest shading or egg relocation (Supplementary
143 Box 1). The aim is to increase the production of male hatchlings to achieve ecologically appropriate
144 sex ratios in the Great Barrier Reef populations, and to help recover Queensland's marine turtle stocks
145 in the long term. Although this will be challenging at large spatial scales, the reduced recruitment of
146 sub-adult males could cause catastrophic population declines within one generation, invalidating
147 more than 30 years of marine turtle conservation efforts.

148 Decision makers can also consider including sex-specific knowledge on the response of species and
149 ecosystems to climate change in prioritization criteria for new marine protected areas. For example,
150 the designation of new Marine Protected Areas may have unintended negative effects on demography
151 and population viability in the illustrative case of species that segregate by sex in warmer years by
152 favoring males or females (Fig. 2). New knowledge from research and monitoring is needed to
153 understand how sex may influence population distribution and dynamics, threats and conservation
154 and management needs across species and ecosystems.

155 Researchers can address the many unanswered questions about biological mechanisms influenced by
156 sex and climate change across species and systems. Research has shown that climate change can
157 induce sex-specific responses both in the presence and absence of pre-existing sex-specific
158 physiological, metabolic, or behavioural differences. Researchers need to disentangle the interactions
159 between sex and climate stressors to understand their relative contribution in the response to climate
160 stressors. This will need specific research design approaches able to test sex and climate change
161 independently and in combination.

162 Moreover, researchers need to focus on how sex-specific responses to climate change at individual
163 level can propagate across systems affecting populations and community interactions. In particular,
164 limited research has focused on community-level consequences of sex-specific differences (Table 1).
165 To advance in climate change biology, researchers will need to include sex in their experimental
166 approaches whenever feasible. In laboratory experiments, sex-based differences are currently tested
167 in less than 10% of ecological studies reviewed^{1,2}, whereas methodological and logistical challenges
168 constrain sex consideration in field research⁴. Scaling-up results from the laboratory to the natural
169 environment is not straightforward, and results about sex-specific differences from field and
170 laboratory experiments can differ². Nonetheless, results from controlled lab experiments may help
171 identifying sex-specific differences and their consequences at population and community levels to
172 be further investigated in natural environments.

173 Funding agencies can incentivize research aimed at producing sex-specific life history knowledge
174 across organisms, populations, and communities, to overcome persistent taxonomic and geographical
175 bias and gaps in biological research³¹ with respect to sex-based differences⁴. This can be achieved
176 through targeted funding schemes supporting basic research to uncover sex-related intraspecific
177 variations of species. Similarly, public institutions and agencies that are leading monitoring programs
178 can include sex as a monitoring variable to support the acquisition of data disaggregated by sex. This
179 “deep peripheral knowledge”³² – the fine detail of biodiversity needed at the species level – can lead
180 to new questions and lines of research in climate change biology at population and community levels.
181 To advance climate change adaptation and mitigation, aquatic and terrestrial biological sciences must
182 analyse males, females and hermaphrodites across their life and reproductive cycles. Individual sex-
183 specific variability in the biological mechanisms of responding to climatic stressors can cascade from
184 organisms to populations and communities. Leveraging this sex-specific knowledge for reversing
185 biodiversity loss through climate-smart policies.

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272 **Figure 1. Examples of sex-based responses to climate change at different levels of biological**
273 **organization.** Sex-specific growth and maturation of Korean chum salmon populations to climate
274 regime shift (a) and of Arctic wolf spiders to earlier snowmelt (b); sex-specific thermal performance
275 of copepods (c) and flying-foxes (d) in response to thermal extremes; sex-specific caloric intake of
276 Pacific walruses in response to climate-induced sea ice reduction (e); sex-specific foraging strategy
277 of caribou facing climate-induced snow cover reduction (f); sex-specific effects of fisheries and
278 climate on the demography of sexually dimorphic birds (g); sex ratio altered by temperature change
279 in reptiles (h); high temperature-induced sex reversal in amphibians (i); shift in timing of sex change
280 in protandrous hermaphrodites induced by ocean acidification (j). Details are reported in Supporting
281 Information (Table S1).

Sex-specific growth and maturation in response to changing climate

Sex-specific thermal performance

Sex-specific energetic bottlenecks in response to climate-induced change

Sex-specific effects of climate change on population demography

Climate-induced effects on sex change

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286 **Table 1.** Examples of cascading effects of sex-based response to climate change, from organisms and
 287 population to communities.

Case study/species	Male vs female differences	Climate effect	Cascading/population effect	Source
Interaction of species with habitat: Valerian (<i>Valeriana edulis</i>) and arthropods	In valerian (<i>Valeriana edulis</i>), a dioecious herb with elevation range from arid low-elevation scrublands to mesic alpine tundra (2000 to 3790 m) of Colorado (USA), female plants were more frequent than males in high elevations because of sex-specific water use efficiency and survival with high water availability.	Because of recent climate-induced aridification, male frequency increased and moved upslope, resulting in greater pollination success and increased seed set for females, facilitating species upslope range expansion.	Since female <i>V. edulis</i> support higher densities of arthropods than do males, including several specialist herbivores that depend exclusively on <i>V. edulis</i> , the effects of a climate-driven decline in female frequency at low elevations may have cascading impacts of associated arthropod communities.	Refs. ^{27,33,34}
Predator-prey interaction: American lobster (<i>Homarus americanus</i>) and fishery catches	In American lobster (<i>Homarus americanus</i>) populations in estuaries, nearshore coastal and offshore habitats of the North-Western Atlantic, sex ratios are skewed towards males in some locations and females in others. Males prefer lower salinity habitats or remain in nearshore and estuarine habitats more than females, which prefer deeper cooler offshore areas. Moreover, fisheries regulations targeting males over reproductive females affect fishing mortality, which depends also on sex-specific catchability and behaviour.	Climate-induced changes in thermal gradients have likely been a key component in the observed changes in distribution patterns.	Projected water temperature increase will likely exacerbate existing skewed sex ratios with effects at local scale, particularly when coupled with sex-specific fishing pressure. These effects will likely influence community diversity and fisheries catches.	Ref. ³⁵
Host-parasite interaction: Meerkats (<i>Suricata suricatta</i>) and tuberculosis infection by <i>Mycobacterium suricattae</i>	In meerkats (<i>Suricata suricatta</i>) of Kalahari Desert (Southern Africa), cooperative breeders living in groups of 2–50 individuals, a type of tuberculosis caused by infection with the species <i>Mycobacterium suricattae</i> is endemic and widespread. Females, evicted by the	Temperature extremes affect clinical tuberculosis occurrence especially in groups that have had a high number of male immigrants in the 5 months preceding the first clinical tuberculosis cases. The probability of group extinction is high with high	Climate change can affect social groups by increasing infectious disease outbreaks, i.e., altering dynamics and interactions between hosts and parasites. Males are likely important carriers of tuberculosis because of sex-specific immunological responses.	Ref. ³⁶

	group dominant female during breeding seasons, return to their group. Males emigrate voluntarily over large distances. These population dynamics may decrease group size and increase female/male ratio in groups, increasing the change of immigration of males.	temperature extremes and male emigration.		
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290 **Text box 1.** Priorities for policy makers, researchers, and funding agencies to advance the field of
 291 climate change biology and ecology towards incorporating sex.

Decision makers:

- Revising spatial prioritization criteria for new marine protected areas in relation to sex-specific knowledge on the response of species and ecosystems to climate change;
- Coordinating management and monitoring in relation to sex-specific knowledge from climate adaptation and mitigation.

Researchers:

- Disentangling the interaction between sex and climate drivers, to understand their relative contribution and effects, and being able to remove sex if not relevant;
- Understanding how individual sex-specific responses to climate change at individual level will propagate across systems affecting populations and community interactions;
- Considering sex and sex-based differences in laboratory and in the field experiments across species and systems.

Funding agencies

- Elaborating funding schemes to support basic research on sex-based differences in species in response to climate change.

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294 **Figure 2.** Example of the identification of a new Marine Protected Area (MPA) considering species
295 distribution not including (map a) and including knowledge about sexual segregation (map b). Some
296 species segregated by sex for foraging in warmer years⁶. If a new MPA (in red) is selected without this
297 information, in a warming scenario the new MPA would protect foraging grounds for males but not for
298 females, and consequently impact population dynamics and viability.

